

World News of Natural Sciences

An International Scientific Journal

WNOFNS 62 (2025) 90-105

EISSN 2543-5426

The bow and arrow in the culture of Brazilian indigenous populations

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ABSTRACT

The bow and arrow are artifacts used by peoples all over the world for thousands of years in hunting, fishing, and warfare. In Brazil, the bow and arrow are still used by some indigenous peoples for hunting and fishing or simply as a piece of craftsmanship. Their making requires great skill. The bow is usually made from flexible wood. The arrow is made of wood or bamboo, with a wooden shard, a piece of bone, or metal attached to its tip. The bowstring is made of plant fiber or vine. It is an ancestral weapon that is important for the culture and survival of these indigenous peoples. This study aimed to learn a little about the cultural richness of some Brazilian indigenous peoples in the making of bows and arrows.

Keywords: Indigenous, ethnoconservation, bow, arrow, indigenous Brazilians

1. INTRODUCTION

The bow and arrow are a fundamental component of the material culture of the human species. For millennia before the bow's emergence, hunters relied on the spearthrower. Humans have continuously inhabited the Americas for approximately fifteen thousand years, during which the spearthrower remained the dominant weapon system for much of that time. Hunters

used it to target the most desirable prey. Around four thousand years ago, the bow and arrow gradually replaced the spearthrower, though both weapons continued to be used in various regions across the planet [1].

The bow and arrow have been, and continue to be, essential tools for the subsistence of many traditional communities, particularly hunter-gatherers. Numerous ethnographic examples illustrate this relationship. However, hunting with a bow and arrow is a highly complex activity, and a hunter's success is dynamic, depending on a range of situational factors [2].

The data presented here were collected during fieldwork conducted as part of several studies on the risks and impacts that infrastructure projects, such as hydroelectric dams, power transmission lines, and highways, pose to the lives of indigenous communities. These studies complement broader environmental impact assessments. This article aims to highlight some of the cultural richness of these indigenous peoples, focusing specifically on the craftsmanship involved in the making of bows and arrows.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study involved Indigenous peoples from the Brazilian Amazon, including the Apiaká, Arara, Juruna (who identify as Yudjá), Kayabi, Tenharim (who identify as Kagwahiva), Mura, and Sateré Mawé ethnic groups, as well as Indigenous groups from the Savannah biome, including the Bororo, Guarani Kaiowá, Guarani Nandeva, and Xavante. The research was conducted with the authorization of the Indigenous communities and the National Indigenous Peoples Foundation (FUNAI), the Brazilian governmental agency responsible for Amerindian interests and culture (Figure 1).

Interviews were conducted with the Bororo in August 2010; the Apiaká and Kayabi in June 2011; the Guarani Kaiowá and Guarani Nandeva throughout 2014 and 2015; the Kagwahiva in October and November 2014; the Mura and Sateré Mawé in January and February 2016 and March 2018; the Arara and Juruna in 2019; and the Xavante in February 2023. One of the study regions is known as the “Volta Grande do Xingu” (Big Bend of the Xingu River), located in the state of Pará, Brazil, between latitudes 03°23'S and 03°38'S and longitudes 51°33'W and 52°00'W. This 130 km stretch of rapids and braided channels on the Xingu River, a major tributary of the Amazon River, is home to Indigenous peoples of the Arara and Juruna ethnic groups.

The Indigenous people of the Kagwahiva ethnic group live in the Tenharim Marmelos Indigenous Land, located entirely within the state of Amazonas, in the municipalities of Humaitá and Manicoré, between geographic coordinates 7°48' and 8°53' south latitude and 61°35' and 62°10' west longitude. In the past, before the construction of the Trans-Amazonian Highway, these Indigenous people lived together in a single village on the banks of the Marmelos River, in the area where the highway now crosses the river.

Indigenous people of the Mura and Sateré Mawé ethnic groups live in the Rio Urubu Indigenous Territory, located in the municipality of Itacoatiara, in the state of Amazonas, on the left bank of the Amazon River. This territory lies between latitudes 02°59'S and 03°12'S, and longitudes 58°04'W and 59°48'W. Other study areas include the Kayabi and Apiaká Indigenous territories.

The Apiaká territory studied is located in Mato Grosso State, in the southern Brazilian Amazon Rainforest, on the left bank of the Teles Pires River, within the Apiacás municipal

district. It lies between 07°39'S and 08°32'S latitude and 57°50'W and 58°21'W longitude. The Kayabi territory studied spans the states of Pará and Mato Grosso, covering parts of the municipalities of Jacareacanga (southwest Pará) and Apiacás (northern Mato Grosso), along the Teles Pires River. It lies between 07°54'S and 09°13'S latitude and 56°39'W and 57°54'W longitude.

Figure 1. Map of Brazil with the approximate location of the Indigenous lands studied and of some cities as reference.

The Indigenous Bororo studied live in the Meruri village, located in the state of Mato Grosso. It is situated between latitudes 15°23'S and 15°44'S, and longitudes 52°51'W and 53°13'W. The indigenous Guarani Kaiowá and Guarani Nãndeva studied live in different

villages located in Mato Grosso do Sul State, near the BR-163 highway, between 21°45'S and 23°12'S latitude and 53°55'W and 54°58'W longitude. The indigenous Xavante people studied live in the Ubawawe Indigenous Territory, located in Mato Grosso State. It lies between 14°23'S and 14°42'S latitude and 53°20'W and 53°38'W longitude.

Data collection was conducted through open and semi-structured interviews [3], allowing for greater flexibility and a more natural dialogue [4]. Indigenous individuals of both genders and various ages, recommended by their communities for their knowledge, were interviewed regarding the making of bows and arrows, the availability of raw materials, and the main uses of these artifacts.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The bow and arrow is an excellent example of how technologies serve as developmental pathways through which human societies organize themselves. Each cultural context in which the bow and arrow is used—whether in warfare, hunting, or sport—demands enhanced musculature, attentive posture, and specialized forms of sensory engagement with the environment [2].

The bow, and arrow, objects traditionally used by the Brazilian Indigenous people for hunting and fishing, are no longer as important today as they once were. Almost always replaced by shotguns in hunting and by rods with hooks in fishing, these objects have come to be venerated as ancestral artifacts and are now presented at gatherings mainly as decorative pieces, helping to keep indigenous culture alive.

The persistence of making bows and arrows among Indigenous peoples, despite the widespread adoption of shotguns, is remarkable. The making and use of bows and arrows are deeply interwoven with the identity of Indigenous men, and for this reason, only a relational-ontological approach can fully illuminate the profound connection between men and their bows and arrows [5].

The Arara, like other Indigenous peoples, make slightly curved bows. These bows made by the Arara are simple, with few ornaments, such as cordage featuring a traditional Arara design on the handle. They are generally crafted from strong yet flexible wood, preferably from the trunk of the *paxiúba* palm (*Socratea exorrhiza*), which produces a distinctive black bow characteristic of the species. Other woods used for making bows include the *pati* palm (*Syagrus cocoides*), which yields a red bow, and the *Handroanthus serratifolius* tree (“ipê-amarelo” in Portuguese). Bowstrings are made from vines or are manufactured from the bark of certain trees, such as species of *Annonaceae*, commonly known as *embiras*. The fiber is removed and soaked in water for a week before being braided to form the string. Crafting a bow follows a process similar to that of an arrow. First, the hardwood is peeled and scraped, then smoked to enhance its durability. Finally, it is meticulously polished using a knife for a smooth finish.

The Arara people make several types of arrows, including the “mumbuca arrow”, which is exclusive to the Itkoum village. It is handcrafted from the stem of the *Astrocaryum gynacanthum* palm tree, known as mumbaca, which grows naturally in the Arara territory. Some arrows are also made from the stem of the taboca, a type of bamboo native to the Amazon rainforest.

Near the rear end of the arrow, feathers are attached to form the fletching, which helps stabilize its flight. The arrowheads used by the Arara and their Juruna neighbors are made from

the barbs of the *paxiúba* (*Socratea exorrhiza*) and *pati* (*Syagrus cocoides*) palm trees, the wood of the *tatajuba* (*Bagassa guianensis*) tree, bamboo, or animal bones—preferably from the shinbone of a deer or its horn, the bone of a capuchin monkey (*Sapajus apella*), or even metal. These arrowheads are affixed to the shaft using fibers from the *croá* leaf (*Neoglaziovia* sp.), a species of the *Bromeliaceae* family.

For fishing arrows, the arrowheads are often designed to be mobile, a feature known as *sararaca*. This mobility helps prevent the arrow from breaking, as fish struck by the arrow tend to swim among branches. With a fixed arrowhead, the force exerted by the struggling fish could cause the arrow to snap. The *sararaca* mechanism helps prevent material loss. The *sararaca* is made from a bamboo stem (*Olyra* sp.) with a chipped tip crafted from the wood of the *maçaranduba* (*Manilkara elata*) tree. The Arara people rarely use the bow and arrow for hunting anymore, but everything comes at a price:

“Now the animals are skittish—they no longer let hunters get close because of the shotgun. Before, hunters moved more slowly, without sudden movements. The animals fed on the fruits of the *inajá* [a species of palm tree], and we could get really close. But now, hunting *nhambu*, *maguari*, *arara*, and *jaburu* [bird species] with a bow and arrow has become difficult” (E.P. Arara, 50 years old, ♂, Arara ethnic group, Itkoum village, Arara's Big Bend of Xingu Indigenous Land, July 12, 2019).

There is a myth that tells how the first deity (*Ñanderuvusu*) presented a series of objects for the Guarani Kaiowá ancestor to choose from, selecting those that pleased him the most. The ancestor chose the bow and arrow, symbolizing society's self-representation as hunters and their preference for a more peaceful nature. The bow and arrow, traditionally used in hunting activities, are primarily regarded as divine artifacts by the Guarani Kaiowá and Guarani Ñandeva. This activity is practiced by both sexes. Bows are made from the wood of the *aguai* (*Chrysophyllum gonocarpum*) and *peroba-rosa* (*Aspidosperma polyneuron*) trees, while arrows are made from the wood of the *aroeira* (*Myracrodruon urundeuva*). However, according to one of the interviewees, the *guariroba* palm (*Syagrus oleracea*) has the most resistant wood for making bows.

The Guarani Kaiowá make two types of arrows: smooth-tipped arrows, which pierce the animal from one side and exit through the other, pinning it to the ground, and serrated arrows, which have backward-facing serrations that penetrate the prey's flesh and lacerate its entrails, killing the animal almost instantly. The choice of arrow type depends not only on the hunter's preference but also on the size and weight of the prey. Among the Guarani Ñandeva, it is quite common for small family groups to sell handicrafts, necklaces, bows (*gyrapa*), and arrows (*ru'y*) in urban centers near their villages. These items are also occasionally sold to visitors.

Bows (*boeiga*) and arrows (*túgo*) are also crafted as handicrafts by the Bororo and hold great cultural significance for this Indigenous people. The bow and arrow serve as essential hunting tools for Bororo. Their production is highly elaborate, involving the careful selection of the finest raw materials found in nature, which determine the quality of the final products. The Bororo not only prioritize the durability of their bows and arrows but also value their aesthetic appeal, as their design is closely linked to the symbolism of each clan. In the complex Bororo social organization, individuals are classified according to their clan, their lineage, and

their residential group. Descent among the Bororo is matrilineal; thus, the newborn receives a name that will identify him/her to his/her mother's clan [6].

To make their bows and arrows, the Bororo use splinters from the trunks of several palm trees common in the Cerrado, such as *tucum* (*bukido*, *Bactris* spp.), *buritirana* (*tugógo*, *Mauritiella armata*), and *babunha* (*Guilielma insignis*), as well as wood from the *aroeira* (*buruduí*, *Myracrodruon urundeuva*) and *coração-de-negro* (*rumága umána*, *Peltogyne confertiflora*) trees. The bows are often adorned with ornaments made from bird feathers and tails. The bowstring is crafted from palm leaf fibers, such as *tucum* (*bukidága*, *Bactris* spp.) and *buriti* (*maridiru*, *Mauritia flexuosa*). Arrows are fitted with wings at the end, and the projectile tip is attached using strips of *imbé* vine (*mikóri*, *Philodendron* spp.). The arrow's wing is typically feathered with macaw or hawk feathers, but feathers from macaws, parrots, curassows, doves, and even chickens are commonly tied or glued along the bow and arrow's body. The materials used for crafting the pointed projectiles attached to the arrows include wood, bamboo, animal bone, and metal. The clan to which an arrow belongs is often identified by its aesthetics.

Bows and arrows are crafted by the Apiaká and Kayabi for both artisanal and recreational purposes, using slivers from the trunks of certain palm trees, such as *inajá* (*Attalea maripa*), as raw materials. The bowstrings are made from woven palm leaf fibers, particularly from *tucum* (*Bactris* spp.) and *buriti* (*Mauritia flexuosa*), as these are more durable. These two palm species are also the most commonly used in arrow production. The crafting of these artifacts is highly intricate, requiring the careful selection of the finest raw materials found in nature, which determine the quality of the final products. This process reflects the aesthetic attention characteristic of these groups. The materials used for the pointed projectiles include wood, bamboo, and animal bones, such as those of the capuchin monkey (*Sapajus apella*).

“The Mura spread out through the forest, anchoring their log canoes, and everyone would go down to places they considered good and beautiful. As a result, the Mura people lost contact and did not experience the same events they were supposed to in the past. They were a people who fought fiercely, but the Portuguese arrived with firearms, while they had only bows and arrows, leading to many deaths. To avoid extinction, they moved down the river” (S.S. Medeiros, 33 years old, ♂, Mura ethnic group, Makira village, Rio Urubu Indigenous Territory, February 3, 2016).

Within the context of this testimony, the Mura stand out due to their significant presence in regions of the Amazon Rainforest. These indigenous people were considered hostile ("savage") by the invading Portuguese. One of their distinctive traits was their bows, which measured approximately 2.5 meters in length, along with arrows of the same size and proportion. When shooting, they did not lift the bow into the air but instead held it to the ground with their toes, allowing them to shoot long distances with precision.

The current bows and arrows of the Mura Indigenous people, who traditionally inhabit the region of the middle Madeira River and the tributaries of the Amazon River, are renowned for their lightness, simplicity, and functionality. The Mura crafted their bows from lightweight, flexible wood, while their long, slender arrows were typically made from bamboo and fitted with tips made of bone, thorns, or metal, depending on their intended use—whether for hunting or warfare. Feathers attached to the rear of the arrows provided greater stability and accuracy

in flight. These weapons served not only as practical tools but also as vessels of technical knowledge and cultural heritage passed down through generations.

The bows of the Mura and Sateré-Mawé are simple and unadorned, typically made from the wood of *maçaranduba* (*Manilkara bidentata*), *itaúba* (*Mezilaurus itauba*), *ingarana* (*Pithecolobium* sp.), and *pau-d'arco* (*Handroanthus* spp.) trees. The wood from these trees is cut, planned, and fired. The bowstrings are made from the inner bark of certain trees, which the indigenous people call *envira* or *embira*. According to the interviewees, the tree species that produce the best *embira* belong mainly to the *Annonaceae* and *Lecythidaceae* families, and their flexibility, strength, and durability are important factors to consider. The arrows can be made with or without feathers.

Among the Sateré-Mawé, a hunter interviewed still uses arrows for hunting. These arrows are made from the stems of a plant in the *Poaceae* family, called *flecheira*. The stems are dried over a fire, and their tips can vary, including tips made of metal or red deer bone (*Mazama americana*). According to the interviewee, arrows are preferred for hunting small prey, which are harder to hit with a firearm. Since he makes the arrows himself, he can afford to miss the target and try again until he succeeds, whereas cartridges are expensive. Therefore, he reserves the shotgun for larger prey, which are easier to hit, allowing him to conserve ammunition.

The bow and arrow, traditionally used by the Tenharim for hunting, no longer hold the same importance they did a few decades ago. Today, they are crafted as decorative pieces and sold to tourists traveling along the Trans-Amazonian Highway who pass through the territory of these Indigenous people. To make the bow, the Tenharim use different types of wood, such as *itaúba* (*agwarayva'yva*, *Mezilaurus itauba*), *pau-d'arco* (*ywete*, *Handroanthus* spp.), and *ameju-preto* (*bodyhyva*, *Duguetia flagellaris*). The bowstrings are made from the bark of certain trees, which the Tenharim call *yvira* (*embiras* or *enviras*). Among the tree species that produce the best *embiras* are some from the *Annonaceae* and *Lecythidaceae* families, such as *yvyriba* (*Eschweilera coriacea*). However, the *embira* from the *apeyba* or *pente-de-macaco* (*Apeiba echinata*) appears to be one of the most commonly used due to its flexibility, resistance, and durability. It is also used in the manufacture of ropes and sleeping hammocks (*tupawa*).

The Tenharim extract latex from the tree known as *ceró* (*araityga*, *Symphonia globulifera*), which hardens when exposed to fire and is used to wax bowstrings as well as strings for crafting. In this process, the tree trunk is cut, allowing the latex to flow out, which is then collected the following day. After being gathered, the latex is boiled and either left in the sun to dry or burned with charcoal. It is then applied to the string. A similar process is used with the aromatic resins extracted from species of the *Protium* genus, commonly known in the Amazon as *breu* (*andevy*). The resin is burned, producing a wax that is used to coat the cotton thread used in arrow-making.

According to one of the Tenharim interviewees, his people use *taboka* (*yrreru*), a type of bamboo native to Brazil, to make arrows, but there is a secret to working with the *taboka* for this purpose:

"You only find *taboka* out in the fields. To get it, you have to go early in the morning to find the male, because the male goes hunting, and only the female stays behind. So yeah, you have to go early to get the male. There's male *taboka* and female *taboka*, and they're different. To make arrows, you have to use the male—so you don't miss your shot. With male *taboka*, you hit your target every time. If the arrow doesn't

kill, it's because it was made with female *taboka*. You have to go early in the morning, and you can't talk too much about where you're going to get it. Then, you have to heat it over a fire to straighten it. You warm it up, straighten it, and make sure it's just right. And while you're working with it, you can't talk too much—if you do, it'll crack or break. That's why we say there are a lot of secrets." (M. Tenharim, 37 years old, ♂, Kagwahiva ethnic group, Hawk clan, Mafuí village, Tenharim Marmelos Indigenous Land, November 8, 2014).

The mysteries and secrets involved in the extraction and crafting of arrows are many, as are the species used by the Tenharim:

"There's a spirit that lives inside the *taboka*, and it has an owner. It doesn't grow just anywhere—only along the road and by the river. It grows out there in the *nhumbiraymuhua*, in the endless fields by Estanho road. When we go into the forest, we have to go in silence. If you cut *taboka* and leave it on the ground, by the time you come back, the owner will have swapped it out for bad *taboka*. Only men can cut it. And you have to know what you're doing to cut it right and take the best part. *Taboka* has male and female, because there has to be a pair to reproduce the spirit that lives inside. If you go in silence, you might see the owners—but only the shamans can really see them. The owner protects the *taboka* with caba bees (a very aggressive kind), snakes, and ants. When we go into the forest, we imitate the calls of *nhambu* (a type of bird) or other animals, so we don't scare anything away. Otherwise, the owner will take the good *taboka* and leave only the bad ones. The bad ones explode when you put them over the fire. The Chief (*tavijara*) is the one in charge, and he has his group. The *erekwarağa* leads the way, and the rest follow: 'I'll take you this way.' Their village is inside the *taboka*. With a bad arrow, you won't hit anything. But with a good one, you can shoot at a fish any way you want and still hit it. But there's a secret to taking *taboka*. You have to go early—if you go after 8:00 AM, you won't find the good *kmajuwa* for making arrows. The story says that the male *taboka* goes out early to hunt. The spotted one is the male, and the swollen one is the female. If you cut a male, you have to tie it up and hold it right away—if you leave it on the ground, it'll disappear. When you go to cut *taboka*, you check if it's female and leave it to reproduce. Only the males are taken. Only the male is good for making arrows that bring hunting success." (J.B.S. Tenharim, 56 years old, ♂, Kagwahiva ethnic group, Hawk clan, Mafuí village, Tenharim Marmelos Indigenous Land, November 12, 2015).

In Xavante culture, the bow and arrow are highly valued pieces of equipment. Once used for hunting, they are still crafted by hand today. The process of making these artifacts is highly intricate, involving the careful selection of the best raw materials found in nature, which directly influence the quality of the final product. The Xavante are not only concerned with the quality

of their bows and arrows but also take great pride in their beauty. They use slivers of palm stems from certain species, such as tucum (*Bactris* spp.) and buritirana (*Mauritiella armata*), as well as wood from aroeira (*Myracrodruon urundeuva*). At one end of the arrow, known as the *contraponta*, feathers from birds such as macaws, parrots, and hawks are attached to help stabilize its flight path. The projectile is fixed at the tip using strips of vine. The raw materials used to craft the pointed projectiles vary and may include wood, *taquarinha* (a type of small bamboo), animal bone, or metal. The bow is carefully worked and finely finished in every detail, often decorated with ornaments made from tail feathers and bird plumes. The bowstring is made from palm leaf fibers, including those from tucum (*Bactris* spp.), buriti (*Mauritia flexuosa*), and buritirana (*Mauritiella armata*).

The Xavante generally hunt using firearms but occasionally use bows and arrows in fire-driven hunts, exclusively within their demarcated territory, as part of ceremonial obligations. In this hunting technique, Xavante set fire to large areas of the *Cerrado* in a horseshoe shape. The surviving animals, attempting to escape the flames, are forced to pass through the narrow end of the "horseshoe," where the Xavante wait with clubs, bows, and arrows. Unfortunately, this form of predatory hunting indiscriminately wipes out all types of animals, including adults and juveniles, those with limited mobility, and even species that are not part of the Xavante diet—such as small rodents, reptiles, amphibians, and microfauna. Additionally, the fire can spread beyond the intended area, worsening the problem of wildfires and destroying large sections of the *Cerrado*, the habitat of numerous animal species.

There does not appear to be a direct relationship between feather color in the manufacture of bows and arrows for most of the Indigenous peoples in our study, as observed among the Awá Indigenous people of the Brazilian Amazon. For these Indigenous people, feathers must be dark (black, gray, or dark brown), such as those from buzzards, harpy eagles, or curassows. Feathers from the many colorful birds that inhabit the forest, such as parrots and toucans, are not used by the Awá [5]. The same applies to other Tupi-Guarani peoples, but not to those belonging to other linguistic families, such as the Kayapó, who do use colorful feathers [7], as do the Bororo and Xavante in our study (all three belonging to the Macro-Jê linguistic stock). Some Tupi-Guarani groups, such as the Kayabi, use arrows with colored feathers, but only in ritual ceremonies [8], which may also be the case for the Juruna and Tenharim in our study.

We observed in the interviews conducted with the Indigenous people that there are many raw materials used in the construction of bows and arrows (Tables 1, 2, and 3; Figures 3, 4, and 5).

Table 1. Main raw materials used by the interviewed Indigenous people in the construction of bows.

Type of raw material	Portuguese name	Scientific name	Ethnicity
Palm trunk chips	Babunha	<i>Guilielma insignis</i>	Bororo
	Buritirana	<i>Mauritiella armata</i>	Bororo, Xavante
	Guariroba	<i>Syagrus oleracea</i>	Guarani
	Inajá	<i>Attalea maripa</i>	Apiaká, Kayabi

	Pati	<i>Syagrus cocoides</i>	Arara
	Paxiúba	<i>Socratea exorrhiza</i>	Arara, Juruna
	Tucum	<i>Bactris spp</i>	Bororo, Xavante
Tree wood	Aguai	<i>Chrysophyllum gonocarpum</i>	Guarani
	Ameju-preto	<i>Duguetia flagellaris</i>	Tenharim
	Aroeira	<i>Myracrodruon urundeuva</i>	Bororo, Xavante
	Coração de negro	<i>Peltogyne confertiflora</i>	Bororo
	Ingarana	<i>Pithecolobium sp</i>	Mura, Sateré Mawé
	Ipê-amarelo	<i>Handroanthus serratifolius</i>	Arara
	Itaúba	<i>Mezilaurus itauba</i>	Mura, Sateré Mawé, Tenharim
	Maçaranduba	<i>Manilkara bidentata</i>	Mura, Sateré Mawé
	Pau-d'arco	<i>Handroanthus spp</i>	Mura, Sateré Mawé, Tenharim
	Peroba-rosa	<i>Aspidosperma polyneuron</i>	Guarani

Table 2. Main raw materials used by the interviewed Indigenous people in the construction of arrows.

Type of raw material	Portuguese name	Scientific name	Ethnicity
Branch	Flecheira	<i>Poaceae</i>	Mura, Sateré Mawé
	Taboka	<i>Olyra sp</i>	Arara, Tenharim
Palm trunk chips	Babunha	<i>Guilielma insignis</i>	Bororo
	Buritirana	<i>Mauritiella armata</i>	Bororo
	Inajá	<i>Attalea maripa</i>	Apiaká, Kayabi
	Mumbaca	<i>Astrocaryum gynacanthum</i>	Arara
	Tucum	<i>Bactris spp</i>	Bororo
Tree wood	Aroeira	<i>Myracrodruon urundeuva</i>	Guarani

Table 3. Main raw materials used by the interviewed Indigenous people in the construction of arrowhead.

Type of raw material	Portuguese name	Scientific name	Ethnicity
Animal bones	Guariba	<i>Alouatta belzebul</i>	Juruna
	Macaco-prego	<i>Sapajus apella</i>	Arara, Juruna
	Veado-campeiro	<i>Ozotoceros bezoarticus</i>	Xavante
	Veado-catingueiro	<i>Mazama gouazoubira</i>	Juruna
	Veado-mateiro	<i>Mazama americana</i>	Arara, Juruna, Mura, Sateré Mawé
	Veado-roxo	<i>Mazama nemorivaga</i>	Juruna
Branch	Taquara	<i>Poaceae</i>	Xavante
Bird's beak	Maguari	<i>Ardea cocoi</i>	Juruna
Coconut shard from palm tree	Marajá	<i>Bactris maraja</i>	Arara
Stingray spine	Arraia	<i>Potamotrygon sp</i>	Arara, Juruna
Metal	-	-	Arara, Bororo, Mura, Sateré Mawé, Xavante
Palm trunk chips	Pati	<i>Syagrus cocoides</i>	Arara
	Paxiúba	<i>Socratea exorrhiza</i>	Arara
Tree wood	Maçaranduba	<i>Manilkara elata</i>	Arara
	Tatajuba	<i>Bagassa guianensis</i>	Arara
	Wood in general	-	Xavante

Within the sequence of activities that constitute the hunting of a wild animal, it becomes evident that the knowledge a hunter applies when using a bow and arrow is directly linked to a comprehensive understanding of the natural environment in which he lives [2]. Observe the instant portrayed in Figure 2, where the bow and arrow are actively employed. The image captures the hunter in exact posture just before letting the arrow fly. He situates himself with one foot ahead, adjusting his body in relation to the target, his eyes locked on the designated point of impact. He then places the arrow onto the bowstring, making sure it is correctly aligned while resting it in his left hand, which also grips another arrow along with the bow. His right hand starts pulling the bowstring toward the right side of his face. As the tension in the string builds, he fine-tunes his stance to keep the arrow in the ideal position for the desired path.

Holding his breath and staying completely silent, he reduces any unintended motion that might affect precision. To fire the shot, the hunter allows the bowstring to slide from his right hand. The arrow is launched forward, yet its course still relies on the hunter's physical control. During the fleeting moment it moves along the shaft, its direction remains affected by the hunter's steadiness. Any inadvertent change in posture at the instant of release—triggered by the abrupt release of tension—can modify the arrow's path as it departs from the bow.

The setting of this specific event is that it was arranged for a representative photographic documentation. However, even in this reenactment, the idea that the cognitive processes at play exist exclusively within the hunter's mind—guided by a pre-established mental model of the action—can be questioned [2]. Striking the target accurately with an arrow depends on a keen awareness of the dynamic interactions between the hunter's body, the bow, and the target.

Figure 2. Hunter from the Tenharim ethnic group demonstrating the use of a bow and arrow. Photo by Fabio Rossano Dario.

Although the target stays motionless, no two shots are ever the same, as the hunter must constantly adapt to the unique conditions of each attempt, including the bow's draw force, the distance to the target, and external elements like crosswind. In an actual hunting situation, the complexity rises considerably due to further environmental variables, making skillful handling of the bow and arrow much more sophisticated than simply estimating range and achieving precision. Pursuing a wild animal in a dense tropical forest demands not only technical proficiency but also the capacity to predict the animal's behavior within its surroundings. Furthermore, it frequently entails collaborative efforts with other community members as part of a larger subsistence approach. A well-placed shot in a hunting scenario represents the result of significant experience and preparation, where the expertise inherent in this practice is deeply intertwined with the hunter's physical interaction with the bow and arrow [2].

Figure 3. (A) Tenharim Indigenous person simulating hunting with a bow and arrow; (B) A Mura Indigenous person demonstrating how ancient Mura warriors held bows with their toes to shoot arrows using a traditional bow and arrows of the Mura; (C) Bororo Indigenous person using a bow and arrow for fishing; (D) Detail of feathers used in the making of arrows by the Arara; (E) Xavante bow and arrow; (F) Borduna (club), bow, and arrow made by the Guarani Kaiowá Indigenous people; (G) Bow and arrows crafted by the Arara with tips from different materials, such as stingray spines, iron, and wood; (H) Arara arrow made with a *taboka* branch (a type of bamboo) and the arrowhead crafted from capuchin monkey (*Sapajus apella*) bone. Photos by Fabio Rossano Dario.

Figure 4. Details of different fletchings, known as the *contraponta*, made with feathers from birds such as macaws, parrots, and hawks, which are attached to help stabilize their flight path: (A) Kaiowá from the Caarapó Indigenous Reserve; (B) Bororo from Aldeia Meruri; (C) Arara from the Guary-duan village; (D) Tenharim from the Trakuá village; (E) Tenharim from the Mafuí village; (F) Tenharim from the Bela Vista village; (G) Tenharim from the Trakuá village; (H) Tenharim from the Taboka village. Photos by Fabio Rossano Dario.

Figure 5. (A) Arara arrowhead made with a stingray spine; (B) Smooth-tipped and serrated-tipped arrows crafted by the Guarani Kaiowá; (C) Mura arrowhead made from a sharpened spoon handle; (D) Different types of arrowheads used by the Sateré Mawé; (E) Mura arrow made with Taboka (a type of bamboo) and a metal tip; (F) Tenharim arrow from the Trakuá village; (G) Tenharim arrow from the Mafuí village; (H) Bundle of Taboka used in arrow making by the Tenharim. Photos by Fabio Rossano Dario.

4. CONCLUSION

The bow and arrow are artifacts traditionally used by Brazilian Indigenous peoples for hunting and fishing. However, they are no longer as essential today as they were in the past, having been largely replaced by shotguns for hunting and by fishing rods and hooks for fishing. As a result, bows and arrows have come to be revered by these Indigenous communities as ancestral artifacts, often displayed at gatherings as decorative pieces, which helps preserve Indigenous culture.

The production of these artifacts relies on various raw materials that Indigenous peoples source from their surroundings, with some differences among ethnic groups depending on their sociocultural and cosmological references. Bows are typically made from strong and flexible wood, while bowstrings are crafted from vines or the bark of certain trees, commonly known as embiras. Arrows are made from the wood of trees, palm trees, and taboca, a type of bamboo native to the Amazon rainforest. Bird feathers are used to create the fletching, which helps stabilize the flight of the arrows. Arrowheads are fashioned from barbed tree and palm wood, bamboo, animal bones, and metal.

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